

Information Organizations and their Websites Performance. A Global Report for Summarization and Optimization Purposes.

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Online Report in Google Data Studio at: <https://datastudio.google.com/s/m0PFz-vS8ZA>

Description of Report:

Now that the ICTs have matured, Information Organizations such as Archives, Libraries, and Museums proceed into the utilization of web technologies that are capable to expand the visibility and findability of their content. Within the current flourishing era of the semantic web, Information Organizations have voluminous amounts of web-based collections that are presented and digitally preserved through their websites.

However, prior efforts indicate that Archives, Libraries, and Museums suffer from fragmentation regarding the determination of well-informed strategies for improving the visibility and findability of their content on the Web (Drivas et al. 2020; Krstić and Masliković, 2019; Voorbij, 2010). Several reasons related to this drawback. As such, administrators' lack of data analytics competency in extracting and utilizing technical and behavioral datasets for improving visibility and awareness from analytics platforms; the difficulties in understanding web metrics that integrated into performance measurement systems; and hence the reduced capabilities in defining key performance indicators for greater usability, visibility and awareness.

In this report, the authors proceed into an examination of 341 unique websites of Archives, Libraries and Museums from all over the world. The initial purpose of this report is to visualize the performance of the websites in terms of technical aspects such as their adequacy to metadata description of their content and collections, their loading speed and security. This constitutes an important stepping-stone for optimization, as the higher the technical capabilities the greater the users' behavior within the examined websites, and thus their visibility and findability level in search engines (Drivas et al. 2020; Mavridis and Symeonidis 2015; Agarwal et al. 2012).

In the first pages of this report, general information is presented regarding the names of the examined organizations. This also includes their type, their geographical location, information about the adopted Content Management Systems (CMSs), and Servers' type of integration per website. Furthermore, several other data are visualized related with the size of the examined Information Organizations in terms of the number of unique webpages within a website, the number of images, internal and external links and so on.

One step further, the authors proceed into the development of several factors that are capable to quantify the performance of websites. Reliability analysis takes place for measuring the internal consistency and discriminant validity of the proposed factors and their included variables. For testing the reliability, cohesion, and consistency of the included metrics, Cronbach's Alpha (α), McDonald's ω and Guttman λ -2 and λ -6 are used.

- For Cronbach's, a range of .550 up to .750 indicates an acceptable level of reliability and .800 or higher a very good one level (Ursachi, Horodnic, and Zait, 2015).
- McDonald's ω indicator has the advantage to measure the strength of the association between the proposed variables. More specifically, the closer to .999 the higher the strength association between the variables and vice versa (Şimşek and Noyan, 2013).
- Guttman's λ -2 and λ -6 work verifiably to Cronbach's α as they estimate the trustworthiness of variance of the gathered web analytics metrics. Low values less than .450 indicate high bias among the harvested web metrics, while values higher than .600 and above increase the trustworthiness of the sample (Callender and Osburn, 1979).
- Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity indicators are used for measuring the cohesion of the involved metrics. KMO and Bartlett's test indicate that the closer the value is to .999 amongst the involved items, the higher the cohesion and consistency of them for potential categorization (Dziuban and Shirkey, 1974).

Both descriptive statistics and reliability analyses were performed via JASP 0.9.2 software.

To this end, this report contributes to the knowledge expansion of all the interest parties and stakeholders related to the research topic of improving the visibility and findability of Information Organizations and their content on the Web. It constitutes a well-informed compass that could be adopted by Information Organizations in order to implement potential strategies that combine both domain knowledge and data-driven culture in terms of awareness optimization on the internet world.

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General Information About Organizations

In this page general information about the examined organizations is presented. On the right side, the pie chart represents the type of examined organizations via percentages. On the table below, the names, the type, the specific address, and the domains of the examined organizations are presented. You can scroll with your mouse within the table to receive further information about each one organization.

	Name of Organization	Type of Organization	Address	Domain
1.	Shaanxi History Museum	Cultural Heritage Organization	91 Xiaozhai E Rd, Xiao Zhai Shang Ye Jie, Yanta District, Xi'an, Shaanxi, China	e.sxhm.com
2.	Museu Nacional d'Art de Catalunya	Cultural Heritage Organization	Palau Nacional, Parc de Montjuïc, s/n, 08038 Barcelona, Spain	museunacional.cat
3.	Art Gallery of New South Wales	Cultural Heritage Organization	Art Gallery Rd, Sydney NSW 2000, Australia	artgallery.nsw.gov.au
4.	National Film and Sound Archive	Cultural Heritage Organization	McCoy Cct, Acton ACT 2601, Australia	nfsa.gov.au
5.	Museu Nacional de Arte Antiga	Cultural Heritage Organization	R. das Janelas Verdes, 1249-017 Lisboa, Portugal	museudearteantiga.pt
6.	The Nelson-Atkins Museum of Art	Cultural Heritage Organization	4525 Oak St, Kansas City, MO 64111, United States	nelson-atkins.org
7.	Toledo Museum of Art	Cultural Heritage Organization	2445 Monroe St, Toledo, OH 43620, United States	toledomuseum.org
8.	Petit Palais Musée des Beaux Arts de la Ville de Paris	Cultural Heritage Organization	Avenue Winston Churchill, 75008 Paris, France	petitpalais.paris.fr

Geographical Locations

On this page, the geo-locations of all the examined organizations are presented. You can pass over the mouse from each dot (.) to check the specific address and the name of the organization. Just like the use of a Google Map, you can zoom-in/out, change from Map to Satellite and of course, you can drag and use the Pegman for the classical Street View.

Content Management System & Server Information

In this page of visualization two pie charts are presented.

- On the left side, several types of Content Management Systems (CMS) are presented. The majority of the examined Information Organizations adopt a Custom approach of websites building, Drupal and Wordpress platforms integration.

- On the right side, the adopted Server Types are presented. Apache, Nginx and Private hosting approaches come as the three most used technologies.

- Below the pie charts, a descriptive table takes place that includes information about each examined website, the adopted CMS and server information as well.

You can scroll inside the table to have a holistic point of view for all the websites.

	Name of Organization	Domain	Type of CMS	Server
1.	Rochester River Campus Library	library.rochester.edu	Drupal	Apache
2.	Museu Nacional d'Art de Catalunya	museunacional.cat	Drupal	Cloudflare
3.	Art Gallery of New South Wales	artgallery.nsw.gov.au	Custom	Nginx
4.	National Film and Sound Archive	nfsa.gov.au	Drupal	Nginx
5.	Museu Nacional de Arte Antiga	museudearteantiga.pt	Custom	Private
6.	The Nelson-Atkins Museum of Art	nelson-atkins.org	WordPress	Nginx
7.	Toledo Museum of Art	toledomuseum.org	Drupal	Nginx

Websites' Size Statistics

This page of visualization depicts the size of each organization. The bigness and architectural complexity of each website is estimated through the number of Pages, Internal and External URLs, number of Images, CSS and Javascript files (Drivas et al. 2020).

On the right side, descriptives of these specific metrics are presented. Shapiro-Wilk and its *p* values are integrated. Shapiro-Wilk test was selected to test the normality of the gathered data in each metric. That is, the closer the metric to .999 and its *p-value* .001, the higher the likelihood to have a dataset with items that follows a normal distribution (Shapiro and Wilk, 1965).

The table below represents the size of each organization. You can scroll inside the table to get further information about the size in terms of Pages, Images Internal, External URLs, CSS and JavaScript files.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics as regards the size of the examined organizations.

	Pages	Internal_URLs	External_URLs	Images	CSS	JavaScript
Valid	341	341	341	341	341	341
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	1585.073	2594.669	932.584	699.352	41.607	52.378
Median	876.000	1688.000	559.000	426.000	14.000	26.000
Std. Deviation	1974.186	2652.190	1096.019	981.373	136.056	124.997
Skewness	2.306	1.707	2.385	3.484	8.311	8.193
Std. Error of Skewness	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132
Shapiro-Wilk	0.679	0.732	0.752	0.602	0.247	0.309
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001
Minimum	1.000	42.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	9835.000	9999.000	7671.000	7089.000	1647.000	1642.000

	Name of Organization	Type of Organization	Pages	Images	Internal_URLs	External_URLs	CSS	JavaScript
1.	Rochester River Campus Library	Academic Library	104	229	375	426	12	5
2.	Museu Nacional d'Art de Catalunya	Cultural Heritage Organization	798	494	1439	559	7	81
3.	Art Gallery of New South Wales	Cultural Heritage Organization	996	701	1026	974	9	12
4.	National Film and Sound Archive	Cultural Heritage Organization	1359	344	1785	212	8	17
5.	Museu Nacional de Arte Antiga	Cultural Heritage Organization	1034	620	1389	611	8	13
6.	The Nelson-Atkins Museum of Art	Cultural Heritage Organization	735	399	1300	700	26	76
7.	Toledo Museum of Art	Cultural Heritage Organization	460	426	1198	781	6	38
8.	Petit Palais Musée des Beaux Arts de la Ville de Paris	Cultural Heritage Organization	506	602	1558	442	8	11
9.	Galleria Nazionale d'Arte Moderna e Contemporanea	Cultural Heritage Organization	515	389	1438	429	17	27
10.	Gallerie d'Italia	Cultural Heritage Organization	1086	443	1702	279	14	40

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Metadata Factor

Page Titles, Headings, and Descriptions

The higher the metadata level, the greater the findability and visibility and ranking of websites in search engines (Drivas et al. 2020; Salminen et al. 2019; Mavridis and Symeonidis, 2015). To this respect, several variables are presented on this page with the purpose to quantify the adequacy of examined websites to cover metadata issues for better visibility and findability.

- Tables 1 and 2 represent the reliability and internal consistency of the involved variables that quantify from 0 to 100 the Metadata condition of the examined websites.
- Table 3 represents the descriptive statistics for each one of the examined variables.
- Table 4 represents information about the metadata factor condition for every website. You can scroll within the last table to have greater information about the condition of each domain.

1

Estimate	McDonald's	Cronbach's	Guttman's 2	Guttman's 6
Point estimate	0.755	0.734	0.775	0.825
95% CI lower bound	0.705	0.691	0.740	0.801
95% CI upper bound	0.795	0.772	0.807	0.856

2

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test ▾

	MSA
Overall MSA	0.626
Set_page_titles	0.519
Use_optimal_length_titles	0.364
Use_unique_titles	0.608
Set_H1_headings	0.601
Use_one_H1_heading_per_page	0.690
Use_optimal_length_H1_headings	0.597
Use_unique_H1_headings	0.662
Set_page_descriptions	0.596
Use_optimal_length_descriptions	0.622
Use_unique_descriptions	0.749

Bartlett's test

X ²	df	p
1845.913	45.000	< .001

Chi-squared Test

	Value	df	p
Model	709.031	26	< .001

3

	Set_page_titles	Use_optimal_length_titles	Use_unique_titles	Set_H1_headings	Use_one_H1_heading_per_page	Use_optimal_length_H1_headings	Use_unique_H1_headings	Set_page_descriptions	Use_optimal_length_descriptions	Use_unique_descriptions
Valid	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	341
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	97.129	62.570	56.880	74.950	58.012	70.853	34.982	36.396	19.537	17.947
Median	100.000	69.000	65.000	94.000	74.000	89.000	23.000	14.000	1.000	0.000
Std. Deviation	13.386	28.282	33.465	35.231	39.847	34.742	34.936	40.230	29.302	28.711
Skewness	-5.994	-0.690	-0.380	-1.272	-0.425	-1.120	0.415	0.523	1.494	1.532
Std. Error of Skewness	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132
Shapiro-Wilk	0.212	0.923	0.898	0.700	0.814	0.763	0.838	0.780	0.709	0.678
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000

4

Name of Organization	Set_page_titles	Use_optimal_length_titles	Use_unique_titles	Set_H1_headings	Use_one_H1_heading_per_page	Use_optimal_length_H1_headings	Use_unique_H1_headings	Set_page_descriptions	Use_optimal_length_descriptions	Use_unique_descriptions
1. Rochester River Campus Library	196	174	172	196	160	192	188	0	0	0
2. Hellenic Mediterranean University	100	80	75	80	75	73	75	0	0	0
3. National Archives of Trinidad and Tobago	100	58	4	80	80	78	4	0	0	0
4. National Film and Sound Archive	100	23	30	91	91	90	21	88	75	18
5. Museu Nacional de Arte Antiga	100	75	11	0	38	0	0	99	0	0
6. The Nelson-Atkins Museum of	100	88	14	15	6	14	2	3	2	0

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Metadata Factor Content Curation

In this page, the descriptive statistics of several variables are presented. These variables related to the technical curation of the content that is included within the examined Information Organizations websites. The first table (1) represents the internal consistency of the factor. The second table (2) indicates the suitability and adequacy of the retrieved web data and their metrics to be categorized into a factor. The third table (3) represents the descriptive statistics of the involved metrics. Lastly, the fourth table (4) articulates individually the performance of each website for the content curation metrics.

1

Estimate	McDonald's	Cronbach's	Guttman's 2	Guttman's 6
Point estimate	0.562	0.538	0.563	0.512
95% CI lower bound	0.462		0.489	0.440
95% CI upper bound	0.606		0.627	0.585

2

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test	
	MSA
Overall MSA	0.649
Avoid_duplicate_page_content	0.645
Avoid_thin_content_pages	0.644
Set_image_ALT_text	0.711
Set_mobile_scaling	0.647
Avoid_plugins	0.471
Set_canonical_URLs	0.693

3

	Avoid_duplicate_page_content	Avoid_thin_content_pages	Set_image_ALT_text	Set_mobile_scaling	Avoid_plugins	Set_canonical_URLs
Valid	341	341	341	341	341	341
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	76.962	68.164	67.513	82.167	98.689	26.070
Median	90.000	85.000	91.000	100.000	100.000	0.000
Std. Deviation	27.661	34.975	40.601	35.449	8.848	41.107
Skewness	-1.339	-0.807	-0.846	-1.771	-9.889	1.047
Std. Error of Skewness	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132
Shapiro-Wilk	0.790	0.813	0.718	0.527	0.125	0.613
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000

Bartlett's test		
X ²	df	p
163.738	15.000	< .001

Chi-squared Test			
	Value	df	p
Model	24.082	9	0.004

	Name of Organization	Avoid_thin_content_pages	Avoid_duplicate_page_content	Set_image_ALT_text	Set_mobile_scaling	Avoid_plugins	Set_canonical_URLs
1.	District Six Museum	99	100	0	100	100	100
2.	Institut National de l'Audiovisuel	99	100	97	99	100	11
3.	Library of Athens School of Fine Arts	0	100	0	0	100	0
4.	Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa	68	100	100	100	100	100
5.	Library and Information Centre of School of Pedagogical and Technological Education	100	0	99	100	16	0
6.	Secrétariat général du Gouvernement du Bénin	74	100	90	0	93	92
7.	Tate Modern	86	100	99	100	100	100

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4

Metadata Factor URLs Condition

This one page of visualization indicates the condition of the URLs inside the examined websites. Complex long-path URLs with symbols and upper or lower case letters could harness the fluidity of the crawling and indexing process by search engines bots. At the same time, broken URLs could lead to higher bounce rate levels while dissatisfying users in terms of information availability and access within websites. In the next tables useful descriptive statistics are presented both in the macro and micro levels regarding URLs condition. In the last table, you can pass over the mouse to check specifically the level of curation for each of the examined websites.

Estimate	McDonald's	Cronbach's	Guttman's 2	Guttman's 6
Point estimate	0.412	0.528	0.552	0.609
95% CI lower bound	0.449		0.488	0.555
95% CI upper bound	0.597		0.616	0.682

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test ▼	
	MSA
Overall MSA	0.615
Use_short_URLs	0.605
Avoid_URL_extensions	0.571
Avoid_URL_parameters	0.532
Avoid_symbols_in_URLs	0.653
Use_lowercase_URLs	0.651
Avoid_underscores_in_URLs	0.670
Avoid_deeply_nested_URLs	0.677
Avoid_broken_internal_links	0.521
Avoid_broken_external_links	0.485
Avoid_broken_page_resources	0.519

Bartlett's test		
X ²	df	p
407.175	45.000	< .001

Chi-squared Test			
	Value	df	p
Model	41.777	18	0.001

	Use_short_URLs	Avoid_URL_extensions	Avoid_URL_parameters	Avoid_symbols_in_URLs	Use_lowercase_URLs	Avoid_underscores_in_URLs	Avoid_deeply_nested_URLs	Avoid_broken_internal_links	Avoid_broken_external_links	Avoid_broken_page_resources
Valid	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	341
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	78.337	73.883	71.762	94.528	88.293	90.085	92.428	73.091	71.416	82.223
Median	92.000	99.000	87.000	100.000	99.000	99.000	100.000	95.000	94.000	99.000
Std. Deviation	26.985	40.215	33.209	17.065	25.226	23.147	18.957	36.949	38.499	32.841
Skewness	-1.392	-1.095	-1.054	-4.061	-2.512	-2.789	-3.034	-1.179	-1.084	-1.814
Std. Error of Skewness	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132
Shapiro-Wilk	0.770	0.633	0.794	0.352	0.518	0.481	0.458	0.696	0.686	0.574
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000

	Name of Organization	Use_short_URLs	Avoid_URL_extensions	Avoid_URL_parameters	Avoid_symbols_in_URLs	Avoid_underscores_in_URLs	Avoid_deeply_nested_URLs	Avoid_broken_internal_links	Avoid_broken_external_links	Use_404_code_for_broken_URLs	Avoid_broken_page_resources
1.	District Six Museum	98	100	100	100	99	100	99	98	100	0
2.	Institut National de l'Audiovisuel	100	98	100	100	93	100	9	85	100	0
3.	Library of Athens School of Fine Arts	100	100	100	100	0	100	0	0	100	100
4.	Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa	68	100	98	100	100	99	99	99	50	97
5.	Library and Information Centre of School of Pedagogical and Technological Education	16	0	16	16	100	0	99	100	99	0
6.	Secrétariat général du Gouvernement du Bénin	8	0	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	40
7.	Tate Modern	95	100	86	100	100	99	99	99	66	100

Speed Factor Curation

Without a doubt, most of us have already been dealt with websites that load their content very slow. Slow loading speed is capable to return immediate abandonments from websites, leading visitors to jump to other ones with greater loading speed performance. In this page, we include some major factors that impact to websites loading speed time. It is noted that this factor indicates lower reliability values. This constitutes an initial one indication that search engines algorithms are willing to integrate additional factors apart from these ones regarding the speed performance of websites (Drivas et al. 2020).

Estimate	McDonald's	Cronbach's	Guttman's 2	Guttman's 6
Point estimate	0.412	0.418	0.449	0.500
95% CI lower bound	0.283	0.323	0.363	0.436
95% CI upper bound	0.509	0.502	0.529	0.576

	MSA
Overall MSA	0.604
Use_valid_HTML	0.584
Use_valid_CSS	0.420
Use_valid_JavaScript	0.589
Avoid_temporary_redirects	0.608
Use_compression	0.600
Use_minification	0.644
Avoid_render-blocking_JavaScript	0.593
Use_long_caching_times	0.611
Avoid_duplicate_resources	0.603

X ²	df	p
112.825	36.000	< .001

	Value	df	p
Model	32.891	27	0.201

Descriptive Statistics

	Use_valid_HTML	Use_valid_CSS	Use_valid_JavaScript	Avoid_temporary_redirects	Use_compression	Use_minification	Avoid_render-blocking_JavaScript	Avoid_resource_redirects	Use_long_caching_times	Avoid_duplicate_resources
Valid	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	341
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	30.789	92.449	99.050	71.012	73.930	55.466	16.792	82.713	41.079	80.754
Median	1.000	100.000	100.000	95.000	99.000	53.000	0.000	99.000	9.000	100.000
Std. Deviation	39.613	17.463	7.887	37.511	41.850	25.025	34.533	34.193	44.760	31.580
Skewness	0.726	-2.833	-10.387	-0.923	-1.126	0.036	1.804	-1.806	0.346	-1.499
Std. Error of Skewness	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132
Shapiro-Wilk	0.721	0.504	0.099	0.742	0.593	0.979	0.516	0.533	0.721	0.652
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000

	Name of Organization	Use_valid_HTML	Use_valid_CSS	Use_valid_JavaScript	Avoid_temporary_redirects	Use_compression	Use_minification	Avoid_render-blocking_JavaScript	Avoid_resource_redirects	Use_long_caching_times	Avoid_duplicate_resources
1.	District Six Museum	0	100	100	100	100	86	0	99	1	84
2.	Institut National de l'Audiovisuel	0	100	100	25	100	92	0	0	0	100
3.	Library of Athens School of Fine Arts	0	100	100	100	0	0	100	100	0	100
4.	Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa	0	100	100	95	100	68	97	100	0	84
5.	Library and Information Centre of School of Pedagogical and Technological Education	100	100	100	100	0	48	0	100	0	100
6.	Secrétariat général du Gouvernement du Bénin	100	100	100	100	100	0	100	100	1	0
7.	Tate Modern	86	100	100	53	98	75	0	99	99	100

Security Factor Condition

This slide includes variables related to the security condition of the examined Information Organizations websites. Practically, not in a few cases, cultural heritage organizations contain e-shops within their websites. This fact demands the establishment of security technologies that foster visitor convenience to explore and buy products. In addition, in archives and libraries, visitors interact with information and sometimes submit their personal data for further services and/or potential news and updates. From a managerial point of view, the compatibility of Information Organizations websites with security factors ensures the intact of their online reputation while avoiding malware and cyberattacks that will inevitably cost economic resources for recovery.

Estimate	McDonald's	Cronbach's	Guttman's 2	Guttman's 6
Point estimate	0.661	0.642	0.667	0.669
95% CI lower bound	0.583		0.617	0.621
95% CI upper bound	0.694		0.711	0.721

	Use_HTTPS	Use_secure_password_forms	Use_HSTS	Use_HSTS_preload	Use_content_sniffing_protection	Use_clickjack_protection	Use_XSS_protection	Hide_server_version_data
Valid	341	341	341	341	341	341	341	339
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Mean	76.050	91.595	13.499	3.211	27.440	40.305	11.862	56.440
Median	100.000	100.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	78.000
Std. Deviation	41.919	27.211	34.168	17.615	39.151	47.868	32.129	45.489
Skewness	-1.232	-3.013	2.146	5.319	0.967	0.383	2.371	-0.231
Std. Error of Skewness	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132	0.132
Shapiro-Wilk	0.549	0.322	0.405	0.168	0.684	0.653	0.382	0.727
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000

	Name of Organization	Use_HTTPS	Use_secure_password_forms	Use_HSTS	Use_HSTS_preload	Use_content_sniffing_protection	Use_clickjack_protection	Use_XSS_protection	Hide_server_version_data
1.	District Six Museum	100	100	0	0	0	0	0	100
2.	Institut National de l'Audiovisuel	100	100	0	0	0	0	100	100
3.	Library of Athens School of Fine Arts	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	62
4.	Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa	100	100	100	0	42	100	0	100
5.	Library and Information Centre of School of Pedagogical and Technological Education	100	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
6.	Secrétariat général du Gouvernement du Bénin	100	100	0	0	0	0	0	35
7.	Tate Modern	100	100	0	0	23	100	0	1
8.	San Francisco Museum of Modern Art	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	5

References

- Agarwal, S., Nishar, D. and Rubin, A.E., Google LLC, 2012. Providing digital content based on expected user behavior. U.S. Patent 8,271,413
- Callender, J. C., and Osburn, H. G. (1979). An empirical comparison of coefficient alpha, Guttman's lambda-2, and MSPLIT maximized split-half reliability estimates. *Journal of Educational Measurement*, 89-99.
- Drivas, I. C., Sakas, D. P., Giannakopoulos, G. A., and Kyriaki-Manessi, D. (2020). Big data analytics for search engine optimization. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 4(2), 5.
- Dziuban, C. D., and Shirkey, E. C. (1974). When is a correlation matrix appropriate for factor analysis? Some decision rules. *Psychological bulletin*, 81(6), 358.
- Krstić, N., and Masliković, D. (2019). Pain points of cultural institutions in search visibility: the case of Serbia. *Library Hi Tech*.
- Mavridis, T, and Symeonidis, A. L. (2015). Identifying valid search engine ranking factors in a Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 context for building efficient SEO mechanisms. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 41, 75-91.
- Salminen, J., Corporan, J., Marttila, R., Salenius, T., and Jansen, B. J. (2019, March). Using Machine Learning to Predict Ranking of Webpages in the Gift Industry: Factors for Search-Engine Optimization. In *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Information Systems and Technologies* (pp. 1-8).
- Shapiro, S. S., and Wilk, M. B. (1965). An analysis of variance test for normality (complete samples). *Biometrika*, 52(3/4), 591-611.
- Şimşek, G. G., and Noyan, F. (2013). McDonald's ω , Cronbach's α , and generalized θ for composite reliability of common factors structures. *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation*, 42(9), 2008-2025.
- Ursachi, G., Horodnic, I. A., and Zait, A. (2015). How reliable are measurement scales? External factors with indirect influence on reliability estimators. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 20, 679-686.
- Voorbij, H. (2010). The use of web statistics in cultural heritage institutions. *Performance Measurement and Metrics*.